

Ericas in Mauritius, home of the dodo

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In *Heathers* 7 (2011), I wrote about the trip I did to Madagascar to hunt for some of the 45 *Erica* species endemic to the island. This was for the major project being undertaken at Stellenbosch University to analyse the DNA of as many species as possible over the whole distribution range of *Erica* in order to work out an evolutionary tree. This project was touched on by one of the project co-workers, Dr Mike Pirie, in *Heathers* 9 (2012) and by me in the talk that I gave to members attending the Annual Gathering in Falmouth in August 2012. In the talk I mentioned the big gap in our knowledge and data for around 50 species from the islands in the Indian Ocean. Fortunately we managed to get material of about 25 species on Madagascar including some possibly undescribed ones. This left us with the three species from Réunion, the two from Mauritius and the single species from the Comoros Islands (between Madagascar and Tanzania). We were in luck when a student from Réunion studying with a friend of ours in Pietermaritzburg kindly collected material of the species on Réunion.

Figure 1. Western Indian Ocean with Madagascar, showing position of Mauritius and Comoros Islands in relation to eastern Africa (Imagery © NASA 2013; TerraMetrics, Map Data © 2013 Google)

In April this year I was attending the Botanical Society's garden fair at Kirstenbosch National Botanical Garden and met my friend Fay Anderson, the botanical artist who did many of the paintings in the "Baker and Oliver" *Erica* book back in the 1960s. She was looking forward to a trip with her family to Mauritius within ten days. I immediately asked her to look out for the ericas which she had seen there on a previous holiday. Then she said that the cottage they were hiring near one of the many fine beaches had two extra rooms so why didn't I join them. Well, the invitation needed no persuasion for me to accept and so I had to organise everything at very short notice. Fortunately the direct flight from Cape Town to Mauritius they were going on had a spare seat for me. One matter that was problematic was the collecting permit as mentioned in the article on Madagascar. "How could I apply just one week in advance?" was the question asked of me by the conservation officials in Port Louis wagging their heads muttering about protocol, etc. Fortunately one very charming young official took me to his office and sorted out everything.

Mauritius is a perfect holiday destination at 20°S latitude, with a subtropical climate, many gorgeous beaches and lagoons lined with coconut palms and very friendly inhabitants. It lies 830km east of Madagascar, with Réunion in between. The two small islands, the Mascarenes, are volcanic in origin with

Figure 2. *Erica mauritiensis* flowers showing the well exserted styles with large plate-like apex with the small stigmatic lobes in their centre and the very long, green, leaf-like bract in each flower (© E. G. H. Oliver).

Figure 3. *Erica brachyphylla* shrubs growing in the cleared area at le Pétrin (© E. G. H. Oliver).

Réunion still active and rising to an altitude of 3,000m. Mauritius was formed 7.8 to 6.8 million years ago and its volcanic activity ceased 25,000 years ago. Since then the volcanoes have eroded away to just 828m high in the north and on the tableland of the southwestern portion of the island. The rainfall varies from 800mm on the dry west coast to 4,000mm per annum on the tableland. Unfortunately, much of the indigenous vegetation which was mostly dense forest has disappeared since the island was inhabited around 400 years ago. Much of the land has given way to agriculture and urbanisation with vast swards of sugar cane dominating the landscape and being the main crop. With humans came the inevitable introduction of alien plants which are having a devastating effect on what is left of the indigenous flora. The worst alien for the ericas is the strawberry guava, *Psidium cattleianum*, which is a major invader on many subtropical oceanic islands. It is estimated that only 5% of the natural vegetation is left, of which only a third is regarded as good quality with few alien invaders.

Figure 4. *Erica mauritiensis* plants growing on a roadside cutting (© E. G. H. Oliver).

The heathland vegetation is restricted to shallow, well drained, rocky soils mainly on the higher parts of the tableland of the Black River Gorges National Park. Pollen studies from cores taken in a few old volcanic craters nearby show that ericas are clearly on the decline and were more dominant 900 years ago. The decline is attributed to an increase in the rainfall.

All the natural flora must have arrived on the island in the last few million years from anywhere around the Indian Ocean. The two ericas however must have come from the west, namely Réunion, Madagascar or the Africa continent because no ericas are known from Asia or Australia. Like the species on Madagascar they all used to belong in the separate genus, *Philippia*, which was characterised by small wind-pollinated flowers with an unequal calyx incorporating the bract. This latter organ may be quite large and sometimes longer than the corolla (see Figure 2). This condition has been found also in some species of *Erica* in the Cape and tropical Africa. In some cases one could find ericoid and philippioid flowers on the same plant. This led to my including *Philippia* under *Erica* in 1988 and required new name combinations and even new names (see below). The Mascarene species were dealt with in 1993.

Erica brachyphylla (the name means “with short leaves”) is very rare and restricted to just two populations. The most accessible one is right next to the office of the Black River Gorge National Park at le Pétrin. The officials there had been advised of my visit and took me to a fenced off area where the heathland vegetation is specially protected (Figure 3) through a project to remove all the aliens, especially the guavas which are abundant around the rim of the gorge. The guava grows there like wheat but is a woody plant to 4m tall. The plants are removed physically, and then Garlan herbicide is applied to the roots. Unfortunately, *E. brachyphylla* flowers in August to October but leafy material was fine for DNA extraction and the species could easily be identified without flowers – the two *Erica* species are distinguished on having leaves in threes or in fours. It formed woody shrubs up to 2m tall. With it grew *Phyllica nitida* (Rhamnaceae), a genus of ericoid shrubs well represented in the Cape Flora around Cape Town.

The other species on the island had been named *Philippia abietina* by Willdenow in Berlin back in 1809. This name could not be transferred to *Erica* since there was already an *Erica abietina* named by Linnaeus from Cape Peninsula. I therefore decided on giving it the epithet *mauritiensis*. This species is more common on the mountains, but is tucked away in places that would have to be reached by some hiking and climbing. Well, on one of our drives around the island visiting many interesting places we were driving up a road to the summit of the Black River Gorge tableland when I noticed some small erica shrublets growing on the steep road cutting near the summit (Figure 4). They turned out to be *E. mauritiensis* and were nicely in flower – not easy to see from a moving vehicle. This population turned out to be a new record for the species and the most southwestern one on the island.

This ‘holiday’ turned out to be very successful for the DNA project.